

A STUDY TO EVALUATE ASSOCIATION OF GENDER WITH CHOLELITHIASIS RISK FACTORS AMONG THE CHOLELITHIASIS PATIENTS

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Abstract

Background: Gallstone disease (cholelithiasis) is a common gastrointestinal disorder worldwide, with prevalence influenced by age, gender, metabolic conditions, lifestyle, physical inactivity and hormonal factors. Women are generally more affected than men due to reproductive and hormonal influences, whereas men often exhibit higher metabolic risk profiles. In Pakistan, gender-specific risk patterns for cholelithiasis are not well-documented.

Objective:

- To determine the association between gender and risk factor of cholelithiasis among diagnosed patients.
- To identify common risk factors of cholelithiasis in male female.

Methods: A descriptive cross-sectional study was conducted from 17 November to 17 January (2) months in the Department of Surgery at Peoples Medical Civil Hospital, Nawabshah. A total of 141 imaging-confirmed cholelithiasis patients were selected using non-probability convenience sampling. Data were collected via a structured questionnaire covering socio-demographics, medical history, lifestyle, and reproductive factors. Statistical analyses were performed using SPSS v25. Frequency, percentage, and chi-square and Fisher's exact tests were applied to determine the associations.

Results: Among 141 participants, 73.05% were female and 26.95% were male, with a mean age of 47.78 ± 9.44 years. Most respondents were from rural areas (86.7%) and joint families (89.4%). Gender was significantly associated with family history of cholelithiasis ($p = 0.012$), hypertension ($p < 0.001$), and smoking ($p < 0.001$). Men showed higher prevalence of smoking and metabolic risk patterns, while women exhibited higher association with family history, reproductive factors, and hormonal influences. No significant gender association was found for prior surgery, hepatitis C, diabetes, or fried food consumption.

Conclusion: Gallstone disease is more prevalent in females, who are influenced

by hormonal and reproductive factors, whereas males are more affected by metabolic risk factors. Shared risk factors include age, blood pressure, and liver disease. These findings highlight the need for gender-specific screening, prevention, and management strategies.

INTRODUCTION

Gallstone disease, also known as cholelithiasis, is a widespread condition characterized by one of The gallbladder is a small pear-shaped sac located under the liver that stores and releases bile that help to digest food whereas bile is a fluid formed in the liver that is crucial for digesting fats and excreting cholesterol while its size ranges from 7–10 cm in length and 3–5 cm in diameter and dysfunction in the physiology of the gallbladder most commonly results in the production of gallstone. Pain from gallstone disease is characteristically severe in the abdomen and is felt in the epigastrium, the right upper quadrant, or both, with a sudden onset that often awakens the patient, while its intensity usually remains constant for 20–30 minutes, may radiate to the upper back, and is frequently associated with nausea and continuous vomiting. The major risk factors for gallstones are classically summarized as the “5 Fs” (female, forty, fatty, fair, and fertile), while additional factors such as age, overweight, hypertension, diabetes mellitus, prior gastrointestinal or bariatric surgery, genetic predisposition, infections, medications, and dietary habits also contribute, moreover fried foods, excessive oil intake, and hormonal therapies, oral contraceptives increase the risk, whereas wine, coffee, fish, and whole meal bread are protective, and family history, oral contraceptive use, and serum lipids are not independent risk factors. The diagnosis should be based on a combination of detailed history, complete clinical examination, laboratory tests, and imaging studies, while abdominal ultrasound is usually sufficient to detect gallbladder stones in patients with symptomatic gallstone disease, whereas the diagnosis of CBDS often requires invasive or non-invasive examinations. Laparoscopic cholecystectomy is indicated for symptomatic gallstones as the risk of recurrence or complications increases over the course of the disease, whereas biliary colic is treated with non-

the most prevent disorder of gastrointestinal tract and it substantially impacts healthcare services. steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs and spasmolytics or opioids can also be used in cases of severe pain. In Europe about one-fifth of the population has gallstones, most (>90%) being cholesterol stones, while black (bilirubin) and brown (bacterial) stones are less common, with risk factors including obesity, female sex, diabetes, and hypertension, and prevalence is ~10–15% in Europe and North America, ~6.1% globally, higher in women and in regions such as South America, and it rises with age, affecting over 25% of women above 60. In the U.S. about 20 million people have gallstones and around 500–600K cholecystectomies gallbladder removals are performed annually approximately 1 million total including all settings and gallstones are more common in women than men with a 2:1 ratio. In Peshawar, gallbladder stones are a prevalent and costly cause of gastroenterological problems among surgical unit and OPD patients at the Lady Reading Hospital, where 55% of the patients were female and 45% were male. In rural areas of Pakistan, the risk of cholelithiasis increases with age, and females demonstrate a higher prevalence with an odds ratio (OR) of 1.4, 95% CI [1.1, 1.7], $p < 0.05$, while obese individuals ($BMI \geq 30$) have 2.2 times higher odds compared to those with normal BMI (< 24.9) (OR = 2.2, 95% CI [1.7, 2.9], $p < 0.001$), the presence of diabetes further increases the odds by 1.6 times (OR = 1.6, 95% CI [1.2, 2.1], $p < 0.01$), and overweight individuals (BMI 25–29.9) are associated with 1.4 times higher odds of cholelithiasis (OR = 1.4, 95% CI [1.1, 1.9], $p < 0.05$). Cholelithiasis is a common condition worldwide, with various recognized risk factors including age, hypertension, diabetes, gender, hormonal therapy, dietary patterns, and family history. In Pakistan, gender-specific risk profiles of patients with cholelithiasis are not well

documented, limiting targeted prevention and management strategies. This study aims to evaluate the association between gender and established risk factors among patients diagnosed with cholelithiasis at a tertiary-care hospital, providing insights that may improve gender specific patient care.

MATERIAL & METHODS

A descriptive cross-sectional study was conducted to evaluate the to identify risk factors association of gender with cholelithiasis risk factors among patients diagnosed with cholelithiasis. The study was carried out in the Department of Surgery at Peoples Medical College Hospital Nawabshah. The duration of the study was two months, from 17 November to 17 January, after obtaining approval from the Institutional Review Board (IRB). The sample size was 141 participants, calculated using the Open Epi formula: $n = Z^2 \times p(1 - p) / d^2$, where n represents the required

sample size, Z is the Z -score corresponding to a 95% confidence level, P is the estimated population proportion of 0.102 (10.2%), and d is the desired margin of error set at 5%. A non-probability convenience sampling technique was used to select the participants. The sample included diagnosed cases of cholelithiasis confirmed by ultrasonography or other imaging methods. Participants belonged to both genders (male and female) and provided informed consent to take part in the study. Pregnant women were excluded due to hormonal influence as a potential confounder. Patients who did not give consent for participation were also excluded. In addition, patients with complicated gallstone disease, such as gallstone pancreatitis, obstructive jaundice, or acute cholangitis, were not included in the study.

RESULTS

Figure 1: Age of respondents

Figure 2: Residence of respondents

Table 1: Religion of respondents

Religion of respondent	Frequency	Percent
Muslim	136	96.5
Hindu	5	3.5
Total	141	100.0

Table 2: Education of respondents

Education	Frequency	Percent
Illiterate	104	73.8
Primary	32	22.7
Middle	3	2.1
Intermediate	2	1.4
Total	141	100.0

Table 3: Ethnicity of respondents

Ethnicity	Frequency	Percent
Sindhi	96	68.1
Punjabi	23	16.3
Balochi	14	9.9
Pashto	1	7
other	7	5.0
other	141	100.0

Table 4: Family type of respondents

Family type	Frequency	Percent
Single	15	10.6
Joint	126	89.4
Total	141	100.0

Table 5: Are you in menopause stage?

Are you in menopause stage?	frequency	percentage
Yes	44	31.2
No	59	41.8
Not Applicable	38	27.0
Total	141	100.0

Figure 3: Economic status of respondents

Figure 4: Gender of respondents

Table 6: Association of Gender with Do you have family history of cholelithiasis?

Do you have family history of cholelithiasis?	Gender		Total %	Fisher's Test	P. Value
	Male %	Female%			
Yes	38 (27.0)	89 (63.1)	127 (90.1)	Fisher's Exact	.012
No	0 (0.0)	14 (9.9)	14(9.9)		
Total	38 (27.0)	103 (73.0)	141 (100)		

Table 7: Are you taking any birth control medication?

Are you taking any birth control medication?	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	70	49.6
Not	33	23.4
Not Applicable	38	27.0
Total	141	100.0

Table 8: Association of Gender with Do you have high blood pressure?

Do you have high blood pressure?	Gender		Total	Fisher's test	P. Value
	Male	Female			
Yes	34 (24.1)	62 (44.0)	96 (68.1)	Fisher test	.001
No	4 (2.8)	41 (29.1)	45 (31.9)		
Total	38 (27.0)	103 (72.0)	141 (100.0)		

Table 9: Association of Gender with Do you smoke?

Do you smoke?	Gender		Total	χ^2	df	P. Value
	Male	Female				
Yes	28 (19.9)	6 (4.3)	34 (24.1)	69.854 ^a	1	.001
No	10 (7.1)	97 (68.8)	107 (75.1)			
Total	38 (27.0)	103 (73.0)	141 (100.0)			

Table 10: Association of gender with study questions (Not significant result).

Serial NO	Questions	Male%	Female%	χ^2	df	P value	Results
1	History of surgery before cholelithiasis?	5 (3.5)	15 (10.6)	0.454	1	0.832	Not significant
2	Hepatitis c?	17 (12.1)	38 (27.0)	0.718	1	0.397	Not significant
3	Fried food consumption?	32 (22.7)	95 (67.4)	1.998	1	0.158	Not significant
4	Diabetes mellitus?	5 (3.5)	26 (18.4)	2.364	1	0.169	Not significant

DISCUSSION

In present study, respondents were aged 30 to 70 years (mean 47.78 ± 9.44), indicating that gallstone disease predominantly affects middle-aged and older adults, These findings correspond with a study at Royal Prima Medan Hospital (2022-2023), where 68.1% of patients were over

40 years, emphasizing age as an important risk factor, The higher prevalence in older individuals may result from cumulative metabolic changes and long-term lifestyle influences.¹¹ In the present study, females constituted the majority of respondents (73.05%) while males represented 26.95%, indicating a higher prevalence of cholelithiasis among women. A similar trend was observed in a hospital-based study from Pakistan,

where cholelithiasis was more frequently identified in females than males among adults aged 20-60 years. These findings reinforce the well-recognized pattern that female gender is a significant risk factor for gallstone disease, possibly due to hormonal influences and associated metabolic factors.¹² Most respondents were from rural areas (86.7%), with only 13.3% from urban areas. This aligns with evidence suggesting higher gallstone risk in rural populations, possibly due to lifestyle, diet, and limited healthcare access. A population-based study in northern Iran also found rural residence associated with increased cholelithiasis risk.¹³ Family history of cholelithiasis was more common in females (63.1%) than males (27.0%) ($p < 0.012$), similar in Lahore study suggesting higher susceptibility due to genetic and gender-specific factors.¹⁴ The present study found no significant association between gender and prior surgery among cholelithiasis patients ($p = 0.832$). However, other research reports more lower abdominal surgeries in females, suggesting possible gender-related differences influenced by population, sample size, or healthcare practices.¹⁵ The study found no significant association between gender and hepatitis C (males 12.1%, females 27.0%; $\chi^2 = 0.718$, $p = 0.397$), which aligns with Egypt study (2023), who reported minimal gender differences in HCV prevalence, although active infection was sometimes higher in adult males.¹⁶ In the present study, fried food consumption was higher in females (67.4%) than males (22.7%), but the association with gender was not significant ($\chi^2 = 1.998$, $p > 0.158$). Similar studies in Pakistan, such as Faheem et al. (2025), found that unhealthy dietary patterns, including fried foods, were significantly associated with gallstone disease, highlighting the importance of overall diet in gallstone risk.¹⁷ In the present study, high blood pressure was more common in females (44.0%) than males (24.1%) and the association was statistically significant ($p < 0.001$). Similar findings were reported by china (2022) and a recent NHANES analysis (2025), showing that hypertension is significantly associated with gallstone risk, particularly in women, highlighting the role of metabolic and

cardiovascular factors in gallstone formation.¹⁸ In the present study, diabetes was slightly higher in females (18.4%) than males (3.5%), but the association with gender was not significant ($\chi^2 = 2.364$, $p > 0.169$). However, previous studies in the U.S. (NHANES, 2025) show that diabetes is significantly associated with gallstone disease, highlighting its role as an important metabolic risk factor.¹⁹ In this study ($n=141$), 31.2% of females were menopausal, 41.8% were not, and 27.0% were male. Evidence from the USA suggests menopause and estrogen exposure increase gallstone risk due to hormonal effects on cholesterol and gallbladder function.²⁰ In the present study, 23.4% of females used hormonal contraceptives, 49.6% did not, and 27.0% were male (not applicable). Hormonal contraceptives may increase gallstone risk in Taiwan also reported higher gallstone risk among users, highlighting their role in gallbladder disease.²¹ In the present study, smoking was significantly more common in males (19.9%) than females (4.3%) ($\chi^2 = 69.854$, $p < 0.001$). Similar evidence from the United States shows that smoking are significantly associated with gallstones in women, with current and former smoking increasing risk in adjusted models. This supports the role of smoking as an important lifestyle-related risk factor in gallstone disease.²²

CONCLUSION

This study aimed to identify the risk factors of cholelithiasis and examine their association with gender among the study population. The findings indicate that cholelithiasis is a multifactorial disease influenced by demographic, hormonal, metabolic, and lifestyle factors.

The age of respondents ranged from 30 to 70 years, with a mean age of 47.78 ± 9.44 years, indicating that gallstone disease predominantly affects middle-aged and older adults. This supports existing evidence that increasing age is an important risk factor, likely due to cumulative metabolic changes and prolonged exposure to lifestyle-related risks. Females constituted the majority of the study population (73.05%), confirming that cholelithiasis is more prevalent among women than men. This gender difference

may be attributed to hormonal factors such as estrogen exposure, menopause, and the use of hormonal contraceptives, all of which influence cholesterol metabolism and gallbladder function. Most respondents belonged to rural areas (86.7%), suggesting a higher burden of cholelithiasis in rural populations. This may be associated with dietary habits, lower socioeconomic status, limited access to healthcare services, and reduced awareness regarding preventive health practices. A strong association was observed between gender and family history of cholelithiasis, particularly among females, highlighting the role of genetic predisposition combined with gender-specific biological factors. High blood pressure showed a statistically significant association with gender, with a higher prevalence among males. This finding emphasizes the contribution of metabolic and cardiovascular conditions to the development of gallstone disease. Smoking was significantly more common among males, indicating lifestyle-related gender differences that may contribute indirectly to gallstone formation. In contrast, no significant association was found between gender and diabetes mellitus, hepatitis C infection, fried food consumption, or history of previous surgery, although these factors remain clinically relevant risk contributors. Menopause and hormonal contraceptive use emerged as important considerations in female respondents, supporting previous evidence that hormonal changes and exogenous hormone exposure increase the risk of gallstone formation.

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